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METAPHORS AND EPITHETS: HOW THEY SHAPE THE WORLD OF RUSSIAN FAIRY TALES

***Abstract:** This article explores the role of linguistic means in creating a magical atmosphere and figurative system of folk art. It analyses how metaphors and epithets not only decorate the text of fairy tales, but also deepen the semantic relations between characters, objects and events. Using examples of classic Russian fairy tales, it is shown how these linguistic elements help to convey emotional mood, reflect cultural traditions and worldview of the Russian people.*

***Keywords:** epithets, metaphors, fairy tales, Russian folk tales, means of expression, linguistic means.*

Russian fairy tales are a unique phenomenon in the world culture, in which traditions, mythology and national identity are intertwined. These works of art are not only interesting in their plot and colour, but are also saturated with vivid linguistic means that give them special expressiveness and depth. Among such means are metaphors and epithets, which play a key role in the formation of the fairy-tale world.

They not only make the text more expressive, but also deepen the understanding of characters, their motivations and relationships, creating a multi-layered structure in which every word has a meaning.

Metaphors, as a means of transferring meaning, open up a wide range of sensory perception and association. They allow readers and listeners to see familiar things from a new angle, creating unique images that are remembered and become part of the cultural landscape. It is not without reason that they are sometimes referred to as hidden comparisons.

Epithets, in turn, are designed to enhance the characterisation of characters and setting, setting the tone and atmosphere in which the action unfolds. The combined use of these linguistic means creates the magic of the text, allowing the reader to dive into a world where the laws of reality are replaced by magic and fantasy.

Consider the well-known Russian fairy tale "The Snow Maiden": Here it is said about the image of the Snow Maiden: "a girl as white as snow", which emphasises her purity and innocence. In this case the metaphor helps us to see the essence of the character.

The Russian folk tale "The Swan-Geese" also uses many metaphors. For example, "geese like dreams", which emphasises that geese are like and symbol of the dream of freedom and safety.

Alexander Sergeyevich Pushkin also often used metaphor in his fairy tales. Here are vivid examples of his figurative comparisons.

"The Tale of Tsar Saltan":

- * "abyss of waters" = deep water.
- * "reveries of the night" = night dreams.
- * "poppies of churches" = church domes.

"The Tale of the Dead Princess and the Seven Rich Men":

- * "quietly blossoming" = imperceptibly becoming more beautiful *
- * "a year passed like an empty dream" = a year passed quickly and aimlessly.

"The Tale of the Donkey and his Worker Balda":

- * "everything dances at him" = any job works out.

There are also so-called zoometaphors, which use animal images to describe human qualities. For example, the image of a pig as a metaphor for greed and low instincts. Or the image of a fox, that is, a cunning person.

Undoubtedly, each fairy tale is saturated with bright and memorable epithets that emphasise the expressiveness of Russian speech. Some of them have already become not only constant, but also used as phraseological phrases.

This is the long familiar "good young man" - denotes an exclamation, an encouraging challenge in Russian folk tales.

"Krasnaya Devitsa" - a beautiful girl with her "golden braid".

"Molodilnye apples" and "living water", capable of returning youth, from A.N. Afanasyev's "The Tale of the Molodets-Udalets, Molodilnye apples and living water".

Epithets are widely used in fairy tales to create a magical world full of adventures and dangers: "Black Forest", "swampy marshes", "wilderness".

In conclusion, metaphors and epithets in Russian fairy tales have not only expressive but also significant cultural function. They help not only to enrich the content, but also convey the spirit of the time in which they were created. Russian folk tales, containing a wealth of linguistic means, help to understand the worldview of the Slavic people, their mythology and philosophy, in which each character is endowed with a unique role.

References:

1. Bogatyrev A.A. Elements of implicit meaning formation in an art text. Tver: Tver State University, 1998. – 101.
2. Dahl V.I. Explanatory Dictionary of the Living Great Russian Language: in 4 vol. M., Drofa, 2011. - VOL.1, VOL.2, VOL.4
3. Dmitrieva I.A. Metaphor as a way of cognition: logical and gnoseological status: Avtoref. dis. . kand. philos. nauk. Yakutsk, 2000. – 16.
4. Gak V.G. Metaphor: universal and specific // Metaphor in language and text / Ed. by V.G. Gak et al. V.G. Gak et al. Moscow: Nauka, 1988. -. 11-26.

5. Kryukova N.F. Metaphor as a means of understanding the meaningfulness of a text: Author's thesis. Cand. of philological sciences.-M., 1988.- 19 p.